

Supplemental Materials for

Instructor-perceived benefits and costs of inviting students to answer questions voluntarily in large science courses

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This supplemental document contains the following:

Items	Page number
Copy of survey questions	2
Copy of semi-structured interview script	4
Table S1. Perceived student-benefits associated with VANQ.	6
Table S2. Perceived instructor-benefits associated with VANQ.	8
Table S3. Perceived student-costs associated with VANQ.	9
Table S4. Perceived instructor-costs associated with VANQ.	10

Copy of survey questions

This survey is completely voluntary and should not take you longer than 5 minutes to complete. Your responses will be anonymous and confidential.

What gender(s) do you identify with? Please check all that apply.

- Woman
- Man
- Transgender
- Non-binary
- Other, please describe
- Decline to state

I most closely identify as

- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Black or African American
- Hispanic, Latino, or Spanish origin
- Pacific Islander
- White/Caucasian
- Other (please describe)
- Decline to state

What is your parent's highest completed level of education? If you have more than one parent with differing levels of education, choose the higher of the two.

- Did not complete high school
- High school diploma or GED
- Some college but no degree
- Associate degree (for example: AA, AS)
- Bachelor's degree (for example: BA, AB, BS)
- Master's degree (for example: MA, MS, MEng, MEd, MSW, MBA)
- Higher than a Master's degree (for example: PhD, MD, JD)
- Other (please describe)
- Decline to state

What is the highest degree you currently hold? Please select the highest.

- Associate degree (for example: AA, AS)
- Bachelor's degree (for example: BA, AB, BS)
- Master's degree (for example: MA, MS, MEng, MEd, MSW, MBA)
- Higher than a Master's degree (for example: PhD, MD, JD)
- Other (please describe)
- Decline to state

What discipline do you currently teach in mainly?

- Biology
- Physics
- Chemistry
- Geoscience

If there is a sub-discipline, please provide that in the blank _____.

How many years of teaching experience do you have? [Fill in]

Have you ever received any teacher training? [Fill in]

What is your current academic position? Please choose your current rank.

- Professor
- Associate Professor
- Assistant Professor
- Other, please describe
- Decline to state

Copy of semi-structured interview script

For the next set of questions, please think back to any science classes that had an in-person component that you taught or co-taught.

Please also think back to any times you have or may have invited your students to answer questions voluntarily in front of the whole class that you posed. This is in contrast with randomly calling on students without warning (also known as cold-call or random call) OR not letting students answer questions at all during class time in front of others.

Before I get started, please take a minute or two to think back to concrete times when you allowed your students to voluntarily answer questions that you posed in front of the whole class. *Instructors had a chance to ask any clarifying questions at this point before moving forward.*

For the purpose of this interview, I will now refer to the practice as students voluntarily answering questions (or when a student raises their hand or gives a signal that they want to volunteer to answer a question).

SCREENING (ALL)

- Do you invite your students to voluntarily answer questions that you pose in front of others in the whole class?
 - How often, how so? (follow-up)

DOES NOT INVITE

- Talk to me about all the reasons why you choose to NOT invite your students to voluntarily answer questions in front of the whole class.
 - What has motivated your decision to NOT use that as a teaching practice?

INVITES

- Talk to me about all the reasons why you choose to invite your students to voluntarily answer questions that you have posed in front of the whole class.
 - What has motivated your decision to use that as a teaching practice?

ALL INSTRUCTORS

- Talk to me about all the possible benefits to students when they are asked to voluntarily answer questions in front of the whole class.
- Talk to me about all the possible disadvantages or drawbacks to students when they are asked to voluntarily answer questions in front of the whole class.
- Talk to me about all the possible benefits to you (as the instructor) when students are asked to voluntarily answer questions in front of the whole class.
- Talk to me about all the possible disadvantages or drawbacks to you (as the instructor) when students are asked to voluntarily answer questions in front of the whole class.

Sample follow-up questions

- To what extent do you consider both student benefits and drawbacks when you decide to use the practice (if at all)?
- To what extent do you consider both benefits and drawbacks to yourself (as the instructor) when you decide to use the practice (if at all)?
- Thinking about your decision to invite students to voluntarily answer questions in front of the whole class, on average, how many times would you say you invite students to voluntarily answer questions you pose in one class setting?

- Talk to me about how you invite your students to voluntarily answer questions that you pose in front of the whole class.
- How confident are you in your abilities to invite your students to answer questions voluntarily in front of the whole class during class time?

Table S1. Perceived student-benefits associated with VANQ. All instructors provided benefit(s) to students.

Student benefits	Full description	n/N N = 21
Enhances learning for all students	<p>Specific to all students: Instructor describes that students by getting to hear responses in student voices, hear wrong answers discussed, hear different perspectives such as new or relevant ways of thinking, have the material reinforced, all students (i.e., those who do not have to "take a risk") stand to learn content through this exercise. This category includes if an instructor talks about the speaker or the audience learning content as a result of the practice like "considering the question or an image" or when all students to get to "test themselves." Further, it includes instances where the instructor may ask "tricky" questions in order to elicit student thinking broadly. This category is specifically about the learning that happens as a result of listening to others. This category includes explaining that asking questions increases students' attention in class, because this is implied as a process by which learning is enhanced (e.g., if student pays more attention, they'll learn more). Instructor reports that having students answer questions can cause (all) students to pay more attention (sometimes described as "be more engaged" or "by eliciting misconceptions the students might have.") This is often discussed as it compares to an instructor lecturing at students, which has been described as "passive." This category includes if a student mentions that this practice provides more opportunities for students to participate (presumably compared to traditional lecture).</p>	15/21
The volunteer builds skills and develops knowledge	<p>Specific to the volunteer: Instructor describes that the participant (i.e., only the volunteer or speaker) gets to practice verbalize/articulate/express and formulate ideas themselves, make new connections between content, think more deeply rather than being passive alluding to those who do not volunteer, "justify" their reasoning and responses, or to test themselves. If an instructor mentions that a student may gain confidence (i.e., "building confidence") or comfort after answering a question, it is coded here because it's assumed that would be a result of skill building. Instructor may also report that students can build confidence if they "get it right." This category is specific to the speaker or the one who volunteers. If the instructor does not specify that it is the speaker or volunteer who learns more or is not asked about the speaker versus audience in a follow-up question, then that would be coded under enhances learning. Further, this category is specifically about the skill-building that happens if someone volunteers even if learning is also happening as a result.</p>	14/21
Creates a comfortable, welcoming, or anxiety-reducing classroom culture for all students	<p>Specific to all students: Instructor describes that the act of inviting students to voluntarily answer questions, or the way that they respond to student responses, can help other students recognize a welcoming, inclusive, or anxiety-reducing classroom culture; this category is about what an instructor does to promote a comfortable environment for potentially all students and is not specific to the speaker (see above) but rather is about the "audience" or those listening. For example, an instructor may imply that they allow students to volunteer as an alternative to cold-calling (i.e., when students are involuntarily called on without warning) for the sake of reducing anxiety, or, they may mention that they practice error-framing (e.g., ensuring students do not feel embarrassed for saying the wrong</p>	9/21

	<p>answer, which could then prompt others to want to volunteer) or practice praising students who participate with the specific intent to welcome participation or to promote comfortable participation in class. This is about the classroom atmosphere and not the speaker themselves but rather the intent to get others to participate. The instructor has to explicitly say the impact to ALL students (e.g., "they" have an opportunity to contribute).</p>	
<p>The volunteer receives positive reinforcement</p>	<p>Specific to the volunteer: Instructor describes that the speaker receives some sort of positive reinforcement, whether that is praise, feedback, or some sort of verbal recognition from the instructor such as "being on the right track", extra points, verbal validation from peers. This includes when instructors describe error framing but ONLY in reference to the speaker (e.g., making mistakes is OK and "making mistakes is how people learn") in a positive way in order to reward the student's contribution to discussion and to actively avoid them feeling embarrassed. This is when the instructor refers to the speaker being rewarded by instructor reinforcement as a result of volunteering to participate; instructor refers to this act by saying "when a student responds" signaling someone is volunteering to answer. This category is sometimes responded to before the instructor goes onto talk about the whole class can benefit (i.e., the latter would be coded in enhances learning for all).</p>	<p>6/21</p>

Table S2. Perceived instructor-benefits associated with VANQ. Of the 21 instructors who provided a response, two (9.5%) did not perceive any instructor-based benefits.

Instructor benefits	Full description	n/N N = 21
Elicits feedback about teaching efficacy	Instructor describes that students answering instructor-posed questions provides insight into whether the instructor is teaching effectively or how they may need to update or pivot their approach. This includes whether they perceive what they have done is effective or not. That is, instructor may receive verbal or non-verbal cues from students after they pose a question that validates their teaching (e.g., head nods from those who may not even volunteer to answer or from someone raising their hand who will go onto volunteer). This category is about an instructor's way to gauge their own teaching or how well they perceive their students are understanding them, and then student learning occurs as a downstream result. This category is about the benefit to instructors ONLY in regard to their teaching.	15/21
Instructor feels more engaged and enjoys the practice	Instructor describes feeling more engaged and that they get enjoyment when having students answer questions because it allows them to see that the student is learning, that students are engaging in class or excited to answer their questions (i.e., even if they are wrong), and instructor gets to see student interests and learn student names, which they describe as enjoyable to them. Instructor mentions that it feels more conversational rather than transactional, which is a positive experience for them. They also mention there is benefit (i.e., to them) in building community and relationships with their students by building relationships (i.e., instructor describes anything related to building a more personal connection with students that can include some sort of dialogue back and forth, which is accomplished when using VANQ).	8/21
Instructor learns something new	Instructor describes that they learn something new from a student when responding, or when preparing the questions they would go on to ask voluntarily or sees a new or different perspective in real-time in class when taking volunteers. This is different from learning about what students know or have learned and is personal in terms of what the instructor knows about a particular topic (e.g., instructor makes new connections). Instructors in this category also describe getting "new examples" motivated from student responses that they can use in their own teaching. This category is primarily about the instructor learning (see above for instructor teaching).	4/21
Attention is diverted from the instructor, and they get a break	Instructor describes that teaching is a performance and by allowing a student to speak it takes the attention temporarily off of the instructor and may even allow for the instructor to accomplish something that they otherwise wouldn't have been able to do when speaking in front of the whole class (e.g. take a sip of water, check the next slide, take a "mental break", keep track of the lecture and material in real-time). Instructors mention this is particularly important in large classes (e.g., over 200 students). Instructor perceives "taking a break" as a benefit because they perceive they have to be prepared for questions, which takes more mental capacity and causes them to be tired compared to using a "flipped classroom approach", which is when students engage before class.	2/21

Table S3. Perceived student-costs associated with VANQ. Of the 21 instructors who provided a response, two (9.5%) did not identify any costs to VANQ.

Student costs	Full description	n/N N = 21
Creates inequities for all students	Specific to all students: Instructor describes that they may only call on particular students who may represent majority groups, and ultimately that those answering questions creates a situation in which the instructor favors students who participate (i.e., instructor reports that "you get the same person volunteering or students hear the same voice.") Instructor also reports that "those who need to speak usually will not." This category also includes if a student feels as though the only person benefiting from the call is the student answering, for example, listeners do not get the "same attention" as the volunteer, and thus, may be more likely to "tune out." It could also favor those students who may enjoy when instructors call on students versus those who do not. Instructor also reports that the problem with one person speaking is there are going to be "limited viewpoints." Further, instructor reports that the work is "not evenly distributed" when only a subset volunteers. Further, instructor recognizes the degree to which students are prepared differently, meaning they could be favoring those with the skill to verbally participate.	12/21
The volunteer is at risk of being negatively evaluated by others	Specific to the volunteer: Instructor describes that speaking up can be any stressful, anxiety-provoking, and/or embarrassing for students (e.g., when the student is wrong they could be judged or penalized). Instructor implies that voluntarily answering a question makes them more likely to be seen, especially in a large class because of the setup of the room and therefore scrutinized (i.e., students listening have expectations of the student speaking), this would be coded here. Instructor also reports downstream effects of being negatively evaluated such as not being able to think, articulate themselves, or learn when in "fight or flight mode." This category is specific to the speaker or volunteer. If an instructor describes why students would not engage, that can be coded here (e.g., student does not engage because anxiety-producing). An instructor may discuss a drawback when they report why a student does not engage, which is coded here if regards how VANQ is anxiety-inducing.	10/21
Wastes class time for all students	Specific to all students: Instructor describes that having students answer questions can waste valuable class time by delaying the delivery of the course material if the instructor is spending time waiting for someone to answer. For instance, if they ask a difficult question, which requires more time to think, or if a student goes in the "wrong direction", and it takes time to redirect thinking, which is for the whole class.	3/21
Introduces confusion for all students	Specific to all students: Instructor describes that having students answer questions can increase confusion among those in class. This can be due to the student's response being confusing, it being hard for other students to hear (i.e., especially depending on where the volunteer is sitting), if the student who volunteers is wrong, or if others in class perceive the instructor summarized something different than what the students said in their answer. It could also be due to an instructor having to "move on" to the next topic while some students may still be on the previous one leading to confusion and lack of clarity.	3/21

Table S4. Perceived instructor-costs associated with VANQ. Of the 21 instructors who provided a response, four (19.0%) did not provide instructor-based costs to the question.

Instructor costs	Full description	n/N21 N = 21
Limits instructor's time to deliver content	Instructor describes that allowing students to voluntarily answer questions can limit the amount of time instructors have to deliver content, which may prevent them from meeting their teaching goals (e.g., getting through a certain amount of content in a set period of time, or ensuring particular topics are covered for pre-med students). This category is not necessarily about the instructor losing their place, but rather an instructor who has a plan and material to cover such that students can learn the material (e.g., MCAT material for pre-meds) and taking questions could "derail the flow of their plan/content delivery" such as rushing the instructor. Instructors in this category may mention "getting off track", but may go onto report it "does not significantly bother them" or negatively impact their teaching approach (i.e., as long as students are learning). However, this category includes anything related to "getting off track." This category does NOT include those reporting on preparation before class.	9/21
Causes the instructor to feel uncomfortable, uneasy or stressed	Instructor describes that opening up the class for discussion can cause an instructor unease, stress, discomfort, or anxiety. This is largely due to transferring control of the classroom to a student, which brings up the unknown of what student will say or do (e.g., going off and doing something else or intentionally avoiding the instructor), and how the instructor will respond in real time such as being the one to re-direct the audience like when someone is wrong or those "in the back of the class listening", or when the same students attempt to answer questions and the instructor is "in a position to decide who to call on." It may also be due to "wait time" where no one is volunteering an answer or when students do not attempt to answer the instructor's question at all, leading to unease or a moment where the instructor is unsure of what to do next.	7/21
Risks damaging student/instructor relationship	Instructor describes that if a student is wrong and the instructor does not handle it in "exactly the right way", it could damage their relationship with the student (e.g., if a student happens to be embarrassed in front of the class). They could be perceived as having embarrassed the student, be perceived as rude, or as condescending. This has to do with the instructor's reputation or students' perception of the instructor as opposed to how the student feels. For instance, the instructor recognizes that how they interact with students matters after they take volunteers to answer questions. The only exception to this would be if how the student feels negatively affects the instructor (e.g., the instructor feels extremely guilty after embarrassing a student or instructor feels like they missed an opportunity to build a relationship with their students.) Instructor perceives that students may view them as favoring particular students or particular student groups, which could jeopardize their reputation or relationships with students, which the latter would be coded here (e.g., especially for those who do not want to stop and take questions). This category does NOT include if an instructor is saying that a drawback is that they're the ones creating inequities because that is a student drawback; UNLESS, they highlight how they personally would be affected such as being "viewed negatively by students". This category is about how the instructor is negatively impacted and NOT students, although both can certainly be impacted.	6/21

Creates extra preparation for instructor	Instructor describes that creating extra questions they would go on to let students voluntarily answer in class, creates extra work that they have to prepare for prior to class. This is ONLY about the preparation prior to class and not about any class time VANQ takes up (see wastes class time above).	2/21
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